

Appraisal of E-Learning Readiness of Academia in Nigerian Colleges: A Study of Federal College of Education, Yola

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Abstract:- Nigeria has been conspicuously lagging behind in digitalization of education process and Colleges are either un-prepared or ill-prepared for switching from physical to virtual methods of teaching and learning. This study investigated the extent of readiness of academic staff towards e-learning in Federal College of Education, Yola. The questionnaire incorporated items that addresses lecturers' readiness, awareness on availability of e-learning facilities, adequacy of e-learning facilities and identifying constraint to e-learning. The questionnaire was administered to 202 academic staff from the seven schools of the College using Taro Yamen sampling techniques. Thus, the researchers integrated qualitative and quantitative methods which combined the use of questionnaire and checklists. The researchers used descriptive statistics to analyse the data. Based on the findings of this study, there is appreciable number of e-learning facilities in FCE Yola indicated by staff irrespective of gender, rank and highest qualification. The study also unveiled low perception on adequacy of internet connectivity, interactive white boards, television sets, centralized internet data subscription, video conferencing facilities, still digital camera and video recorder. Moreso, academic staff are not willing to bear burdens on running e-learning off campus and computer maintenance. However, they are available for further training and opened to adapting new technologies and innovations on e-learning. For optimum utilization of these facilities, the College Management should organize seminars and workshops for academic staff. Government should provide all the necessary tools that assist the adoption of e-learning. Staff computers be maintained and upgraded, this is very necessary to meet the demand and efficiency in adopting e-learning.

I. INTRODUCTION

Colleges of Education are tertiary institution established to producing professionally trained teachers for our grammar, vocational and technical secondary schools in Nigeria. There are federal colleges of education, state colleges of education and private colleges of education. These colleges can be classified into colleges of education technical, colleges of education non-technical and college of education (special). Colleges of Education Technical are established to train teachers in the area of vocational and technical education, aimed at providing trades and technicians for our industries,

while Colleges of Education non-technical are established to train teachers in general education and colleges of education (special) are established to train teachers to teach students with learning challenges. According to Federal Republic of Nigeria FRN (2014) in Asogwa *et al* (2022), all colleges of education are supervised by the National Commission for Colleges of Education (NCCE).

Federal College of Education, Yola (FCE Yola) is located in Yola North Local Government Area of Adamawa State and occupies a land of 155 hectares along the Jimeta-Yola Road. FCE Yola is one of the fastest developing institutions of higher learning perfectly situated in the North East zone of Nigeria. The vision of the College is to be a leading world class college for teacher education Since the year 2000, there have been dramatic changes in the nature of higher education, (Biggs and Tang 2011). It is not just that participation rates are higher than ever, but that these and other factors have altered the main mission of education and modes of delivery." This means that new pedagogical approaches are being sougheed with a view to delivering high-quality education. The Bologna Process (2010) of 1999 has a profound impact on the delivery of high-quality education. Since then, there has been a clamour for teaching effectiveness which has intensified over the years. It is felt that higher education learning and teaching must move away from teacher-centred strategies and embrace student-centred approaches due to the increase number of tertiary-level students who possess different learning abilities.

E-learning is one significant way to cater for diverse learning styles. It is all about getting students to move away from the full face-to-face modality in favour of virtual environment where each and every one would be able to work at one's pace. Brown (2005) establishes that since the introduction of internet-based education, there has been a rapid improvement in student learning outcomes.

The best approach to be adopted to achieve effective learning is known as pedagogy, (Hussein & Chalabi, 2020). The creation of multi-faceted pedagogical practices through the utilization of ICTs can empower students and learners to achieve higher learning and interaction (Aljaber 2018). One effort in creating a good pedagogical system is what is called computer-supported collaborative learning (CSCL) which is intended to create dominant learning and communication atmosphere via the application integrated collaborative

learning and ICT (Lin & Lin, 2019). The CSCL can drive better peer interaction and group work, promote higher levels of dissemination and sharing of knowledge and expertise within the learning society (Lukas & Yunus, 2021). Pedagogy is fundamental and instrumental in achieving well-desired learning outcomes (Manazir & Rubina, 2020). Pedagogy thus needs the teacher to understand how students learn to integrate, design and deliver course materials and mentor students adequately, (Ananga, 2020). Pedagogy is therefore instrumental and the cornerstone to the development and diffusion of e-learning technology since without it the desired learning outcomes cannot be achieved (Monjaraz-Fraustro et al., 2021). E-learning systems must be designed to meet the different approaches to pedagogy especially in areas of such as individual and group interaction and online assessment (Ananga 2020).

Appraisal is a diagnostic activity that helps one to determine the extent to which a system is able to meet its targets or objectives. Trembley, *et al* (2012) described appraisal as the gathering of evidence that would help to make decision to improve a program, planning, budgeting or policy. Appraisal of the e-learning readiness for this study refers to the extent to which FCE Yola is prepared or ready to use e-learning training and education in terms of students' readiness, lecturers' readiness and availability of e-learning facilities.

II. PROBLEM STATEMENT

Federal College of Education, Yola was established by the Ministry of Education in the year 1974, to provide qualitative, effective and competent based middle-level teachers for Nigerian Secondary Schools that can compete globally. The Vision of the College is "To be a leading world class College for Teacher Education". Hence, this calls for re-structuring in the area of pedagogy for better quality education as spelt out in the vision statement.

The College is conscious of the rapid technological changes around the world, regarding tertiary learning and teaching. Though the College is aware of these imminent changes, implementation is extremely slow. e-learning is not yet enforced as an alternative instructional delivery mode. In fact, face-to-face teaching is still the only mode of instructional delivery. Teacher-centered strategies are still current. The delivery of quality education at FCE Yola is still a very big issue and this is impeding the promotion and enhancement of learning that matters.

Government has made efforts to make ICT facilities available for both administrative and academic activities in the College. It is saddening to observe that most academic activities appear to be carried out through traditional methods in the College. Therefore, this study intends to assess the extent to which the College is prepared or ready to use e-learning in the teaching and learning process.

➤ Objective of the Study

The long-term objective of the study is to appraise the e-learning readiness of academic staff and students, availability of e-learning facilities, constraints and solution to the implementation of e-learning in FCE Yola. The specific objectives are: To

- Investigate the awareness of academic staff and students on the availability of e-learning facilities in FCE Yola
- Determine adequacy of e-learning facilities in FCE Yola
- Determine e-learning Competency of academic staff in FCE Yola.
- Determine level of willingness of staff to bear burdens that go along with e-learning

➤ Research Questions

- What is the awareness on available e-learning facilities in FCE Yola?
- Are e-learning facilities adequate in FCE Yola?
- How competent are the academic staff of FCE Yola for e-learning?
- What are the constraints to implementation of e-learning in FCE Yola?

III. LITERATURE REVIEW

According to Garcia et al. (2018) "E-learning is an approach to teaching and learning which is dependent on the use of electronic system or media and devices as tools to improve the access to education, training, communication, interaction and to facilitate the development of new methods to learning and teaching". This imply that, e-learning is the use of ICTs to improve and support teaching and learning process, (Yoloye and Nwokefor, 2015). E-learning is vital in conventional education due to its flexibility, broad resources-sharing capacity and cost-effective scalability. E-learning can be compartmentalized into two; learning and technology, (Aparicio et al., 2016). The learning part is seen as the cognitive process for attaining knowledge and new skills while technology serves as a powerful enabler of the learning process, (Aparicio et al., 2016).

E-learning system are based on the concept of Computer-Assisted Instruction, (CAI) and the theoretical framework of the development of an e-learning system is based on three major components of information system such as people, technology and services, (Aparicio et al., 2016). Any developed e-learning system must interact with its intended users and thus e-learning technologies provide the direct or indirect interaction of different categories of peoples and users, (Aparicio et al., 2016). The technological aspect seeks to provide technical support to ensure the integration of content, enable communication and availability of collaboration tools, (Aparicio et al., 2016). In terms of the services part of an e-learning system, e-learning services and activities are designed to align with the e-learning pedagogy and instructional modalities and strategies, (Aparicio et al., 2016).

Electronic readiness (e-readiness) is simply a measure of the degree to which a community or group of people may be ready, willing or prepared to obtain the benefits arising from the use of e learning and technology. Machado (2007), defined e-readiness as the “state of play” of a country’s Information Technology (IT) infrastructure and the ability of its consumers, business and government to use Information and Communication Technology to their benefit. Schunk and AL-Huneid (2012) defined e-readiness as the degree to which an economy or community is prepared to participate in digital economy. E-readiness is often used to measure how ready a country, community, organization or person is ready to partake or participate in electronic activities such as e-learning and training.

This study is concern with the assessment of e-readiness of academic staff and students to participate in electronic teaching and learning.

IV. METHODOLOGY

The methodological approach to be adopted to conduct the study will be mixed methods, (Creswell, 2003). The mixed methods approach employs strategies of enquiry that involve collecting quantitative and qualitative data either simultaneously or sequentially. The study is of an exploratory nature as the objective is to find out the readiness of staff and students to the introduction of technology based-education.

➤ *Population/Sampling*

The total population of the study came directly from FCE Yola community, 409 academic staff. A sample of 202 academic staff was used. This sample was drawn from the

entire students and staff population in the College using Taro Yamen sampling formula as cited by Israel (2015)

$$n = \frac{N}{(1-N)(e^2)} ; \text{Where } N=\text{total population, } e = \text{error (0.05) and } n = \text{sample size}$$

This sampling is synonymous with qualitative research. This kind of sampling technique has been chosen, as the intention is to survey specific groups of individuals (staff and students) of the College. In this case, to herein after make judgments on the information gathered regarding the specific phenomenon in question, in this case, E-learning. In other words, the focus is on these groups of people since they will best enable the researchers to answer the research questions.

➤ *Data Collection Method and Instrument*

The data collection involved gathering numeric information (e.g. facilities) as well as text information (e.g. surveys), so that final database represents both qualitative and quantitative information. The instrument for the collection of data was structured questionnaire and check list. The checklist was designed by researchers to obtain information on the availability of e-learning facilities in the College. Two Structured questionnaire was developed, one for academic staff having five (5) sections on demography, awareness, adequacy, competency and willingness to bear some burdens on e-learning. The second questionnaire was for students consisting of three (4) sections, namely demography, awareness and competency on e-learning facilities. These questionnaires were developed and validated by experts in computer and computer maintenance. Instrument will be validated by experts. Data was analyzed with SPSS software using descriptive statistics.

V. RESULTS

➤ *Analysis of Demographic Information.*

Fig 1 Demography of Respondents

➤ *Sex of the Respondents*

In Figure 1 above, the distribution of respondents by sex varies, out of the 201 participants 119 are male which constitute the majority by 59%. While female participants are 82 at 41%. The males are majority of respondents because most of the participants in the various school of the College are males. However, the female participants are not proportional but sizeable in all the schools.

➤ *Age Bracket of the Respondents*

Figure 1 above shows the distribution of respondents by age bracket, 70 participants were within the age 40-49 constituting majority of the respondents which represents 35%. They were followed by those in the 50-59 years age bracket indicating 64 participants representing 32%. They are closely followed by 30-39 age bracket indicating 55 respondents representing 27% while very few are within the age bracket 20-29 years indicating 8 participants representing 4%. For 60 years and above age bracket, only 4 participants responded representing 2%. However, this study shows that, most of the respondents are within the age range of 30-59 years constituting 93% of respondent.

➤ *Rank of the Respondents*

Figure 1 shows the distribution of respondents by their rank which varies. Out of the 201 respondents, 44 participants are Lecturer III, representing 22%. They were closely followed by Assistant lecturers, 39 participants responded representing 19%. Thirty, (30) Principal lecturer responded representing 15% of the respondents while 26 of the participated were lecturer I representing 13%. Out of the 201

participants 17 were chief lecturers representing 9% while 16 senior lecturers participated representing 8% of the total respondents. This shows that all rank is well represented.

➤ *Highest Qualification of Respondents*

Figure 1 presents the distribution of respondents by academic qualification. Only three levels of education were represented. Academic staff with Bachelor degree formed the majority of respondents. They form 40% of the total respondents. Holders of master degree formed 31% of the respondents while holders of doctor of philosophy degree formed 29% of the total respondents.

➤ *Teaching Experience of Respondents*

Figure 1 above shows teaching experience of respondents which varies. Out of the 201 participants 91 of the respondents served between 1 to 10 years representing 45.3% of staff followed by those that served between 11 to 20 years, 53 participants representing 26.4%. Next were those who serve between 21 to 30 years, 32 participants representing 15.9% of total respondents and lastly 25 participants served above 30 years representing 12.4% of respondents. On the average most of the staff of the College have teaching experience within 1 to 20 years.

- Research question one, to investigate Staff awareness of the availability of e-learning facilities at FCE Yola For an institution to be e-learning ready, her Academic staff must be aware of all the e-learning facilities. Information from the lecturers gave the following state of the College.

Table 1 Mean value of Respondents on perceived Awareness of E-Learning Facilities

S/N	Item(s)	Aware		Not Aware		Mean	SD	Remarks
		No	%	No	%			
1	Desktop/Laptop Computers	182	90.5	19	9.5	1.91	0.29	High perception
2	Smart/Interactive White Board in Classrooms	111	55.2	90	44.8	1.55	0.50	Low perception
3	Internet Access points	150	74.6	51	25.4	1.75	0.44	High perception
4	Library online resources	161	80.1	40	19.9	1.80	0.40	High perception
5	Centralized internet data subscription	69	34.3	132	65.7	1.34	0.48	Low perception
6	Computer based Test Centers	185	92.0	16	8.0	1.92	0.27	High perception
7	Institutional E-mail	166	82.6	35	17.4	1.83	0.38	High perception
8	Video conferencing facilities (e.g.NgREN)	40	19.9	161	80.1	1.20	0.40	Low perception
9	E-Classrooms for lectures	100	49.8	101	50.2	1.50	0.50	Low perception
10	Lecture recording equipment	66	32.8	135	67.2	1.33	0.47	Low perception
Weighted (Sample) Mean						1.61		

Table 1 indicates the mean value of respondents' responses on awareness, on the availability of e-Learning Facilities. Furthermore, the result in the Table is on different associated determinants of awareness on e-learning facilities availability. On the perceived awareness of the participants, the most perceived determinant in terms of availability is the CBT centers in the College with mean value of 1.92 which is above the weighted mean of 1.61. Other determinants with reasonable level of perceived awareness on facilities availability are: desktop/laptop computers with mean value of 1.9, institutional email with mean value of 1.83, library online resources with mean value of 1.80 and internet access point with mean value of 1.75. All these determinants mean value are above the weighted mean of 1.61, this indicates a high

level of perception and awareness on the availability of the availability of e-learning resources in the College.

However, the perceived awareness of the respondents on the availability of internet facilities on some of the determinants are within the range of the weighted mean in terms of their mean values, except awareness on the video conferencing facilities that is not encouraging with the mean value of 1

This means that staff moderately aware of the e-learning facilities in the College. This study is in agreement with the result obtained by Asogwa, Nkanu & Sabo (2022) that most of the e-learning facilities are available in colleges of

education and awareness is very necessary. This research work is also similar to the work of Datuk and Ali (2012) according to them, in order to enhance the effectiveness of e-learning, there are many challenges that needs overcoming and this include awareness. Their study revealed that there is still lack of awareness amongst some academic staff on available e-facilities. However, this study is contrary with the

study of Oye et al (2011), that e-learning in Nigeria institutions has not developed due to a number of factors and according to them there is mass unawareness.

➤ *Analysis of Objective two, to Determine Adequacy of FCE Yola e-Learning facilities*

Table 2 Mean Score of Respondents (Staff) on Perceived Adequacy of E-Learning Facilities

S/N	Item(s)	VA		A		I		GI		Mean	SD	Remarks
		No	%	No	%	No	%	No	%			
1	Computers	46	22.9	106	52.7	44	21.9	5	2.5	2.96	0.74	High perception
2	Printers	23	11.4	72	35.8	102	50.7	4	2.0	2.57	0.72	High perception
3	Internet Connectivity	18	9.0	39	19.4	113	56.2	31	15.4	2.22	0.81	Low perception
4	Interactive white boards	11	5.5	47	23.4	99	49.3	44	21.9	2.12	0.81	Low perception
5	Projectors	20	10.0	73	36.3	96	47.8	12	6.0	2.50	0.76	High perception
6	Television sets	10	5.0	32	15.9	107	53.2	52	25.9	2.00	0.79	Low perception
7	Library online resources	39	19.4	91	45.3	56	27.9	15	7.5	2.77	0.85	High perception
8	Centralized internet data subscription	22	10.9	62	30.8	97	48.3	20	10.0	2.43	0.82	Low perception
9	Computer based Test Centres	34	16.9	126	62.7	41	20.4	0	0.0	2.97	0.61	High perception
10	College Website	42	20.9	89	44.3	51	25.4	19	9.5	2.77	0.89	High perception
11	Institutional E-mail	65	32.3	92	45.8	37	18.4	7	3.5	3.07	0.80	High perception
12	Video conferencing facilities (e.g.NgREN)	4	2.0	37	18.4	108	53.7	52	25.9	1.97	0.72	Low perception
13	Still Digital Camera	7	3.5	41	20.4	108	53.7	45	22.4	2.05	0.75	Low perception
14	Video Recorder	4	2.0	37	18.4	126	62.7	34	16.9	2.05	0.66	Low perception
Weighted (Sample) Mean										2.46		

Key: VA=Very Adequate; A=Adequate; I=Inadequate; GI=Grossly Inadequate

Table 2 indicates the mean value of respondents' responses on perceived aadequacy of e-learning facilities. Furthermore, the result in the Table is on different associated determinants of the adequacy of e-learning facilities. On the perceived adequacy of the participants, the most perceived determinant in terms of adequacy is the institutional email with mean value of 3.07 which is above the weighted mean of 2.46. Other determinants with reasonable level of perceived adequacy of facilities are: CBT centers with mean value of 2.97, computers with mean value of 2.96, College website and library resources with mean values of 2.77 respectively. All these determinants mean value are above the weighted mean of 2.46, this indicates a high level of perception and awareness on the perceived adequacy of e-learning resources in the College.

However, the perceived adequacy of the respondents on some of the determinants are within the range of the weighted

mean in terms of their mean values, except adequacy on the video conferencing facilities that is not encouraging with the mean value of 1.97. Other determinants below the weighted mean are: internet connectivity with mean value of 2.2, interactive white boards with mean value of 2.12, television sets with men value of 2.00, centralized internet data subscription with mean value of 2.43, still digital camera and video recorder with mean value of 2.05 respectively indicating that these items are not adequate.

The findings is in line with the study of Mac-Ikemenjina, (2005) as cited in Anene, Imam and Odumuh (2014) that inadequate e-learning facilities includes bandwidth access, digital camera,video recorder, software packages, inadequate training facilities at the tertiary level. In corroboration, Oye *et al* (2011) added that there is inadequate or non-availability of internet access and limited bandwidth in most tertiary institution.

➤ Analysis of Objective 3, Determine E-Learning Competency of Academic Staff in FCE Yola.

Table 3 Response of Staff on their Perceived level of Competency on E-Learning Items

S/N	Item(s)	I		SI		SC		C		Mean	SD	Remarks
		No	%	No	%	No	%	No	%			
1	Installing and uninstalling applications on devices	19	9.5	44	21.9	61	30.3	77	38.3	2.98	0.99	Low perception
2	Create, Save and exit documents	22	10.9	17	8.5	58	28.9	104	51.7	3.21	1.00	High perception
3	Create and manage files and folders in computer	33	16.4	20	10.0	38	18.9	110	54.7	3.12	1.14	Low perception
4	Ability to edit a document (Bold, italicize and underline, change font color, Cut, copy and paste text or graphics)	36	17.9	20	10.0	33	16.4	112	55.7	3.10	1.17	Low perception
5	Save files into Google drive/sky drive/ iCloud	27	13.4	38	18.9	52	25.9	84	41.8	2.96	1.07	Low perception
6	Save files into flash drive or CDs.	15	7.5	28	13.9	56	27.9	102	50.7	3.22	0.95	High perception
7	Print documents	41	20.4	13	6.5	28	13.9	119	59.2	3.12	1.21	Low perception
8	Use antivirus to protect computer	33	16.4	21	10.4	78	38.8	69	34.3	2.91	1.05	Low perception
9	Download and view documents and files	23	11.4	12	6.0	47	23.4	119	59.2	3.30	1.01	High perception
10	Make and edit slides	29	14.4	31	15.4	61	30.3	80	39.8	2.96	1.06	Low perception
11	Use PowerPoint for presentations	35	17.4	35	17.4	44	21.9	87	43.3	2.91	1.14	Low perception
12	Prepare documents using word processor	30	14.9	43	21.4	52	25.9	76	37.8	2.87	1.08	Low perception
Weighted (Sample) Mean										3.16		

Key: I=Incompetent; SI=Somehow Incompetent; SC=Somehow Competent; C=Competent

Table 4 Response of Staff on Perceived Level of Competency on E-Learning Items, Cont'd

S/N	Item(s)	I		SI		SC		C		Mean	SD	Remarks
		No	%	No	%	No	%	No	%			
13	Use spreadsheet to perform mathematical calculations on statistical data	45	22.4	71	35.3	45	22.4	40	19.9	2.40	1.04	Low perception
14	Open internet explorer and other web browsers	25	12.4	21	10.4	37	18.4	118	58.7	3.23	1.07	High perception
15	Searching for information using different search engines	21	10.4	19	9.5	51	25.4	110	54.7	3.24	1.00	High perception
16	Composing, attaching file and sending email messages	19	9.5	9	4.5	51	25.4	122	60.7	3.37	0.95	High perception
17	Accessing Emails	18	9.0	8	4.0	39	19.4	136	67.7	3.46	0.93	High perception
18	Download and save files online	22	10.9	15	7.5	18	9.0	146	72.6	3.43	1.03	High perception
19	Use the social media to get updates on academic field of study	18	9.0	8	4.0	44	21.9	131	65.2	3.43	0.93	High perception
20	Text-chatting	19	9.5	7	3.5	27	13.4	148	73.6	3.51	0.94	High perception
21	Voice-chatting	18	9.0	23	11.4	19	9.5	141	70.1	3.41	1.01	High perception
22	Video-chatting	21	10.4	18	9.0	30	14.9	132	65.7	3.36	1.02	High perception
23	Video conferencing	28	13.9	28	13.9	40	19.9	105	52.2	3.10	1.10	Low perception
Weighted (Sample) Mean										3.16		

Key: I=Incompetent; SI=Somehow Incompetent; SC=Somehow Competent; C=Competent

➤ *Perceived Level of Competency of Staff on E-Learning Components*

The analysis on Table 5 shows that majority of the respondents agreed that they can create, save and exit documents, they can also save files into flash drive or CDs, also they can download and view documents and files. These set of responders are of the opinion that they are efficient in opening of internet explorer and other web browsers, searching for information using different search engines, composing, attaching files and sending email messages, and can access their email messages with ease. They are also competent in downloading and saving files online, uses the social media to get updates on academic field of study, proficient in text chat, video chat and voice chatting. On the other hand, most of the participating academic staff had a low perception with regards to installing and uninstalling applications on devices, creation and management of files and

folders in computer, ability to edit a document (Bold, italicize and underline, change font color, Cut, copy and paste text or graphics) and inability for them to save files into Google drive/sky drive/ iCloud. They find it difficult to print documents, cannot use antivirus applications to protect their systems, make and edit slides, use PowerPoint for presentations in their lectures and prepare documents using word processor. They reported low perception in the use of spreadsheet application for mathematical calculations, statistical analysis and video conferencing.

These results are consistent with the study of Alomari (2023) and Huda et al. (2017), which showed that the degree of teachers’ achievement of e-learning competencies in Gaza schools were moderate. It differed from the study of Al-Enezi (2021) and Harijanto et al. (2021), all of which were conducted in an Arab environment.

➤ *Analysis of Objective 5, to Identify the Constraints to E-Learning in FCE Yola*

Table 5 Response of Staff on Readiness to Bear Some Burdens in Order Promote and Sustain E-Learning Project in the College

S/N	Item(s)	SD		D		A		SA		Mean	SD	Remarks
		No	%	No	%	No	%	No	%			
1	Buy data for running e-learning programme off-campus	36	17.9	49	24.4	104	51.7	12	6.0	2.46	0.85	Low perception
2	Always keep laptop in working condition	28	13.9	21	10.4	112	55.7	40	19.9	2.82	0.91	Low perception
3	Create more time to organize for online lessons	10	5.0	27	13.4	108	53.7	56	27.9	3.04	0.78	High perception
4	Keep track with the timeline and other demands that come with E-learning	2	1.0	32	15.9	129	64.2	38	18.9	3.01	0.62	Low perception
5	Adopt E-learning as any hurdles related to it are corrected gradually	14	7.0	24	11.9	110	54.7	53	26.4	3.01	0.82	Low perception
6	Avail self for more training on E-learning	2	1.0	18	9.0	83	41.3	98	48.8	3.38	0.69	High perception
7	Adopt new technology and innovation on E-learning	0	0.0	4	2.0	109	54.2	86	42.8	3.41	0.53	High perception
Weighted (Sample) Mean										3.02		

Key: SD=Strongly Disagree; D=Disagree; A=Agree; SA=Strongly Agree

➤ *Willingness of Staff to Bear Some Burdens in Order Promote and Sustain E-Learning Project in the College*

From Table 4, majority of the responders had a high perception that they are willing to create more time to organize online lessons, make themselves available for further training and open to adapting new technologies and innovation on e-learning. However, most others are of the opinion that, they are not willing to buy data for running e-learning programme off-campus and cannot afford to always keep laptop in good working condition, they are unable to keep track with the timeline and other demands that come with E-learning and it may likely affect their willingness to Adopt E-learning as any hurdles related to it are corrected gradually. The findings is in line with Asogwa *et al* (2022) and Ololube *et al* (2007) who found that the most significant of these constraints are inadequate computer maintenance, inadequate training and retraining of staff on the use of e-

learning software, limited internet access and band width, substandard facilities and electricity among others.

VI. CONCLUSION

Based on the findings, it was revealed that most staff of the college are aware on some of the e-learning facilities available in the college such as desktop/laptop computers, white board, internet access points, online library resources and computer base test center. Furthermore, findings from the study revealed that other facilities like centralized internet data subscription, college email, video conferencing facilities, e-classroom and recoding facilities for lectures, staff are not aware of the availability of such facilities.

The study also revealed that both categories of respondents are competent enough to manipulate some basic computer operation except that of installation and uninstallation of application on the computer device.

Staff reported low perception in the use of spreadsheet application for mathematical calculations, statistical analysis, video conferencing, are not willing to buy data for running e-learning program off-campus and cannot afford to always keep laptop in good working condition. They are unable to keep track with timeline and other demands that come with E-learning and it may likely affect their willingness to adopt e-learning.

Moreso, findings revealed that students are either somehow competent or incompetent in spreadsheet (Microsoft excel) and Microsoft PowerPoints. On internet operation, students are competent in some internet application except composing, attaching files and sending them to emails.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this study, there is appreciable number of e-learning facilities in FCE Yola. For optimum utilization of these facilities, it is recommended as follow:

- The College Management should encourage Staff to keep updating themselves through periodic awareness campaign and workshops of the e-learning facilities that the College have
- Awareness sensitization is necessary for both male and female irrespective of their highest qualification, teaching experience and rank. The young lecturers, (age bracket 20-29) require awareness through orientation exercise or seminar on the availability of e-learning facilities in the College
- The Government and FCE Yola Management should provide the following e-learning facilities which are inadequate, internet connectivity, interactive white boards, television sets, centralized internet data subscription, video conferencing facilities, still digital camera and video recorder. Inadequacy of the listed items are indicated by both male and female irrespective of their age bracket, rank, teaching experience, highest qualification and school. These e-learning facilities are very necessary for e-learning to commence in the College
- Training and re-training of Academic staff should be periodically carried out to boost capacity particularly in the use of Microsoft Office Applications
- Internet access point to be spread across the campus for constant and consistent access by academics
- Adequate motivation be put in place to encourage Academic staffers to be acquire data for use even at home
- ICT capacity should be made a requirement on APER Form for staff promotion to encourage more commitment to the use of e-learning across all levels of staff

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